

A Study on Indian Diaspora Literature with Ecocriticism

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Abstract:

A study of the "Diaspora Space" shows how an individual's identity is formed, where inequality arises, and how physical, mental, and social attitudes affect and build identity. Not only personal identities but also relationships with one's homeland have changed dramatically in recent decades. It has lost its stability and immigrants are becoming global citizens. Everyone in the Diaspora tries to open their niche in the host country, but everyone does it their way. An analysis of diaspora space and other diaspora-related identity issues can help us understand how and where identities are formed, and how and where differences are made and reconstructed.

It is a well-accepted fact that the basic theme of all literature is human being, his or her actions, thoughts, feelings, beliefs, and faiths. Literature deals with the number of sociological concepts, arrangements aesthetically. Diaspora literature deals with emigrant sensibility. It focuses on the lives of immigrants and their inner and external conflicts in an alien land. By highlighting issues like cultural predicament, quest for identity, multiculturalism and universal aspects of human existence, Diasporic Literature occupies an important status in the literary field.

The present study is an attempt to present the Indian Diasporic responsiveness that statistics in Indian literature in English.

Keywords: Indian Diasporic responsiveness, Diaspora Literature, Indian Diaspora, Enlightenment of Diaspora

Introduction:

The concept of Diaspora has been derived from the Greek word meaning "to scatter." Moreover, the word is associated with the dispersion of the Jews beyond Israel. Hence, the diaspora belongs to a scattered population with a common origin in a smaller geographical area. It means migration of a specific population across cultural domain where the uprooted people feel nostalgic about their homeland. It does not mean that they have no home; but having home on an alien land becomes a means of suffering for them. Therefore, they see and feel the difference of living at home and abroad. The simple and single definition of the term is not

possible because the concerned field of diaspora is changing its paradigms with respect to the changing modes of technologies in the digital age. Scholars must not think that diaspora has been lost due to the invented means of super technology. On the contrary, the basic assumptions have been changed slightly; yet there is a lot of scope to study it again. Now, the people's sufferings have some additional tools and means by which they provide much scope in the field of research. This scope strikes with traditional structure of diaspora changing it in new dimensions and forms.

The Diaspora is a process of people migrating frequently from one place to another for various reasons. Migrations have resulted in building up a diasporic community which shares a common sense of rootlessness, pain, and agony of homelessness in a new land. Cultural interactions paved the way to establish multi-cultural societies. The policy of multi culturalist is often contrasted with the concept of assimilation and social integration. All diasporic discourses are shaded by the ideology of post-colonialism. In the present global scenario, many people migrate in search of employment, business, and trade.

All diasporic communities established outside their birth territories concede that their own native land always has some claim on their loyalty and emotion. This occurs through language, religion and custom. The diasporic people often find themselves managing across cultural identities. They must create various cultural, ethnic, and political identities to meet the challenges from their native lands and their adopted homelands. The way in which the diasporic people manage their identities is determined by political, social, professional and class factors. The diasporic communities might choose adoption, accommodation, acculturation, and assimilation. Identity crisis arises if one migrates from one territory to another place.

Diasporic identities are manifold, heterogeneous, and subject to persistent metamorphosis. While they attempt to adopt themselves to their various experiences, they simultaneously endeavor to find their identity. The compromise among these multiple, mobile, and altering identities can be sorted out by the formation of a transcultural identity. Diasporic discourse compels us to contemplate about fundamentals of nation and nationalism, while determining the affinities of citizens and nation state. Diasporic discourse mirrors awareness that living is a part of transnational network that involves a homeland. Diaspora discourse speaks about people who reside in one place but passionate for another place. Another aspect of

diasporic discourse is the search for selfhood in the world between two cultures that of homeland and embraced land. The notion of ‘home’ often plays a cardinal function in Diaspora communities. In migrating from one nation to another, the migrant quests for setting up home in a new land. But they are unable to identify the new place as their home. Instead, they find their home elsewhere, back across the boundary and they always wish to come back. The emigrant must start his next beginning wherever he goes to settle. In **M.G.Vassanji’s** *Amrika* at the end Ramji would neither adjust with life in America nor exposes the dynamics of east African-Indian life in a new country, he feels strangely depleted.

‘Hybridity’ is one of the concepts of diasporic discourse. Homi J Bhabha clarifies in his essay “*Science Taken for Wonders*” about hybridity. “The relation between mother culture and alien cultures produced through the strategy of repudiation, the reference of discrimination is always to the process of splitting as the condition of subjection: a discrimination between the mother culture and its bastards, the self and its doubles, where the trace of what is discovered is not repeated but respected as something different – a mutation, a hybrid.” Bhabha’s contention is that there is an amalgamation of cultural forms because of two processes of colonialism and post-colonialism. His notion of hybridity is one of the universal experiences of the colonized. Diaspora and its impact give rise to corresponding attitudes to the literature. The immigrant or expatriate writers produce literature which reflects thrust areas such as family, sexuality, nationalism etc. which can be judged in terms of Western concept of what is genuine and what is false.

Ecocriticism has been defined in numerous ways leading to complexity that the term carries. It started with the aim of raising concern towards nature through literature, but its scope and definition has become much broader since then. The term is new, but not the concern. The concern is centuries old. Nature’s importance for the existence of life on earth has been given valuable space in the religious books of the world. It has been revered and its value is emphasized in almost all the religions.

The term ecocriticism, however, was first used by William Ruckert, in 1978 in his essay *Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism*, by which he meant — the application of ecology and ecological concepts to the study of literature. Later it became wider and more included everything that was related to the physical world. Many were a part of this journey.

There are many intellectuals in the theoretical world working on this terminology. Their continuous efforts have led to the expansion of the meaning of the term; this has made it more inclusive. Homo sapiens have been utilizing natural resources for centuries but there is no account when use turned into abuse. Men started exploiting their own survival agent. They forgot that their existence depends on ecology of which they are just minute parts. This what Rachel Carson meant when she said, the most alarming of all man's assaults upon the environment is the contamination of air, earth, rivers, and sea with dangerous and even lethal materials. This pollution is for the most part irrecoverable; the chain of evil it initiates not only in the world that must support but in living tissues is for the most part irreversible.

Indian Diaspora was mainly a special choice of individuals, particularly for academic pursuit or economic gains either towards the Middle East or to the Western countries, particularly to U.S.A. The deportee did face a clash of opposing cultures, a feeling of alienation which was then followed by the attempts to adjust, to adopt, to accept and finally form a disconnect identity as a racial group to be assimilated and hence uncultured. All this is placed under the umbrella term of deportee Writing or Diasporic Literature.

The term originally associated with the Jewish chronological experience but today the term has acquired a more expanded meaning and it refers to common inherited homeland, voluntary or involuntary migration and a sense of peculiarity in the country of residence. This term cuts across various disciplines such as Sociology, Cultural Studies, and Political Science etc. On the background of globalization, the term 'Diaspora' raises the questions of acculturation, assimilation, the loss of identity etc.

The immigrants, whatever their reason for migration be, financial, social, political, no matter whether they migrate for trade and commerce, as holy preachers, as laborers, convicts, soldiers, as expatriate or refugees, exiles, or as guest workers in search of recovered life and opportunities have shared some common things as well as differences which are based on their conditions of migration and period of stay in the adopted land. Mostly the migrants suffer from the pain of being far off from their homes, the memoirs of their motherland, the anguish of leaving behind everything familiar agonize the minds of migrants.

The expatriate literature also deals mostly with the inner quarrel in the context of cultural dislodgment. The immigrants away from the families swing between crisis and renovation. They

are thrice alienated from the native land they left behind, from their new crowded country and their children. Diaspora literature is in constant conversation with the meta home. The longing to regain lost home often culminates in the creation of a different description of home.

Nostalgia, loss, betrayal, and duty are the basics of new homes as diasporic protagonist adjust to new countries. In adjusting to new countries, issue of acculturation and assimilation become the central point as these immigrants consult the unbalance of their hyphenated identities. Usually, the generation diaspora cling to food and clothes as the most apparent markers of Indianness that sets them apart and highlights their difference. The assertion on this difference is often a conscious declaration of belonging to another place. On the other hand, second generation diaspora declines and removes such identity markers to assimilate the prevailing culture.

The terms 'Nation' and 'Identity' become necessary to examine the way of living life and human existence, in the past and present. Problems of the nation, identity, national identity, individual identity, etc. are the recent needs, which have surface, which were never qualified by mankind in the past. The life that people lived in the past was mainly introvert with themselves and their families. It is not essential for one to take it for arranged that the problem of nation and identity take place in the life of person only when he accepts migration and mobility. Since, it is a psychological feeling; there is a possibility of its experience even within his native land.

Identity becomes the core issue in any exploration of diaspora. The diasporic identity is based on the history or circumstances leading to migration, as well as the individual responses to these circumstances. There are some factors like language, dress, and socio-cultural environment that deepen the problem of nation and identity after immigration takes place.

Two of the earliest novels that have efficiently depicted diasporic Indian characters are **Anita Desai's *Bye Bye Blackbird*** and **Kamala Markandaya's *The Nowhere Man***. These novels reveal how racial prejudice against Indians in the UK of 1960's isolates the character and deepen their sense of displacement. **Bharati Mukherjee's** novels like *Wife and Jasmine* depict Indians in the US the land of immigrants both legal and illegal before globalization got its thrust. **Salman Rushdie** in his novel *The Satanic Verses* approach the metaphor of immigration by adopting the technique of magic realism. **Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni** in her novel *The Mistress of Spices* depicts Tilo, the protagonist, as an exotic character to reveal the migrant's

distress. **Amitav Ghosh's** novel *The Shadow Lines* shows the extent of rootlessness encountered by a character born and brought up on a foreign land. **Amit Chaudhari**, in his novel *Afternoon Raag*, portrays the lives of Indian students in Oxford. These writers also depict the positive aspect of displacement. There are benefits of living as a migrant, the opportunity of having a double perspective of being able to experience assorted cultural modes. It is often this advantage that enables diasporic Indians, particularly of the second generation; face the dilemma of dual identities. Such ambivalence produces existential anguish in their psychology.

Markandaya, had a strong dedication to expose the cruel reality of life to effect the beloved change in society. Nationalism, detachment, Poverty, Peasantry, Subjugated Women, Rural-Urban Divide, East-West encounter, Feudal Practices, Casteism, and Communalism were some of the themes quite closer to their hearts. All of them are well known for pragmatic portrayal of existing Indian life. Taking departure from the first generation of Indian English novelists, the postmodern Indian English novelists have concentrated on a completely new set of themes which are wide ranging and inclusive as the life in the age of globalization is immersed in the talented issues of globalization and subsequent multiculturalism, feminism, queer theories, diasporic emotional response, glamour, consumerism, commoditization, upward mobility, erosion of ethical values are some of the main issues raised by fashionable novelists and short stories writers.

The problem of racial antagonism took a terrible form in America for the South Asians and especially for the Sikh diaspora after 9/11 which has been obtainable by **Chitra Banerjee-Divakaruni** in her novel *The Queen of Dreams* (2004) where a second-generation Sikh young man Jaspal is given malicious punches by a few American youths, though he keeps on crying that he is an American like them. This is an unconfident situation of the diaspora identities, creates a question before the diaspora theorists of diaspora identities as to which nation do the diaspora belong. The nation which their parents and grandparents had once left to settle in the other one or the one that they had adopted and which never acknowledged them from the heart.

A few Indian diaspora writers like **Jhumpa Lahiri** in *The Namesake* and in her short story *The Last and Final Continent* and Kavita Daswani in her *For Matrimonial Purpose* (2003) have portrayed positive aspects of diaspora experience which make wider the scope of the perception and bring change in the subjectivities of their characters. Through their

protagonist they have described that cultural dealings not only opens new routes for them connecting to culture of new location and of their homeland but also makes them mobile carrier of cultures and ways of thinking to both the lands and more lands and make a good mixture of these, thus creating new third cultures and shaping third history.

Indian American literature is among the very 'young' literature in the United States, hardly forty years old. Writing by immigrants from the Indian sub-continent is associated with personal and communal individuality, memories of the homeland, and the active retort to this 'new' world. Writers express their personal, ancestral identities and socio-political context, explaining how and why they come to be where they are and to write what they do. **Ved Mehta's** autobiographical inquiry in *The Ledge between the Streams* deals with his personal and familial detailed in an old-fashioned way.

Bharati Mukherjee widens the autobiographical convention of Ved Mehta in quite different ways. Society is the subject matter of her memoir, *Days and Nights in Calcutta*, co-authored with her husband. It is a work in which Mukherjee reveals her wistfulness for her home city.

Bharati Mukherjee is one of the prominent refugee writers who reject the tradition-bound society of the East as she reaches out for the more empower and characteristic society of the West. Her novel *The Tiger's Daughter* depicts a young women's unsettling return home to Calcutta after years abroad. The wife is about the despair of an immigrant woman of middle-class Bengali origin devoid of her support configuration in a foreign society. *Darkness* portrays the despair produced by the encounter with Canadian racism. Her *Middleman* and *Another Stories* reveal immigrant experience in US and Canada in ironic vein. Mukherjee's later novel *Jasmine* shows the potential of remaking oneself in the New World.

American Born confused Desi (ABCD) is a term that refers to people of Desi origin, living United States. 'Confused' refers to their confusion, regarding their identity having been born in America or lived there since babyhood and been more closed to American culture than to their native culture. Their bonds in India are arbitrate by their parents. This second generation is more aware of struggles of people of color in the United States and attempt to review the inequalities of race and class. Another point that should be noted is that second generation women often find that they are subject to more affectionate demands and limitations than their

male counterparts. Dating often becomes a scratchy issue in the lives of teenage daughters. Conflicts faced within the home by the Indian American women are the subject of **Sushama Bedi's** novel *The Fire Sacrifice* and is an inveterate theme of fiction and poetry in the recent anthologies.

The exclusive thing about Indian diasporic writings lies in the fact that the Indian diaspora differ from another diaspora. Unlike other Asian diaspora, the Indians, despite being 'Indian' do not reluctantly share a common faith, language, fare, dress, etc. The result is that the variety we have in India gets echoed in the literature of the writers of different background typically based on regions and sometimes on castes and religions.

Rohinton Mistry writes in a different way from Jhumpa Lahiri or other Indian writers living and writing abroad. Writers write about the customs, traditions, dress, and cuisine, unusual to the region from where they come. In a way, they bring same rich miscellany that we have in India in their writings by portraying the microscopic details of their rites, dress, cuisine, etc. into the literature that they create. The comprehensive handling of the fish or the depiction of the vermilion in Jhumpa Lahiri creates 'Bengaliness' or Rohinton Mistry can portray Parsi habits and traditions. These regional sub-groups make Indian diasporic literature in English somewhat unique and different.

Unlike Bharati Mukherjee, Chitra Banerjee - Divakaruni, and Sunetra Gupta, Jhumpa Lahiri is a class apart in the sense that her second-generation diasporic location does not bond her to Calcutta (Kolkata) by birth. Born in London, raised in Rhode Island, Connecticut and presently living in New York, she deals faithfully with dislocation and disappointment of immigrant's lives also showing Bengali strain in them. All the nine stories of her debut literary work *Prophet of Maladies* set in America and India are unified by the pattern of exclusion, loneliness, and search for fulfillment. They do not confine themselves only to the experiences of migrants and displace individuals. Though she speaks about universal appeal, most of Lahiri's Indian characters are Bengalis and her prose spotted with details of conservative Bengali names, food, cooking, and wardrobe, giving character and flavors to her stories. Also, as a Bengali, the idea of marriage loom large in her life. Lahiri initially drew heavily on her experiences of Calcutta as it gave her a discernment of her inheritance. Through this perspective, she credibly portrays the universal nature of human existence that goes beyond the boundaries of region, religion, nation, etc.

Before analyzing her literary works, it is essential to take note of Jhumpa Lahiri's special and literary profile.

The diasporic tension is not only spatial (torn between nation/cultures) but also temporal (split between the past and the present). **Homi Bhabha** has also underlined the pain involved in the act of remembering: remembering is never a quite act of introspection or retrospection. It is painful remembering, a putting together of the dismembered past to make sense of the trauma of the present. In Indian panorama, this specified area enwraps the uprootedness of people from their native lands to serve the British Empire, and in post-colonial situations, people from the third world countries left for the developed countries leaving their home lands. This immigration caused these immigrants an experience of sense of uprootedness and unbelonging in the new lands. This plight of Diaspora reflected in writings. Diaspora writings have portrayed specific conflicts revealing the heterogeneity of Indian culture.

Diasporic Studies as an academic discipline lies at the intersection of several increasingly powerful developments in new literatures. Interdisciplinary and comparative scholarship has become prevalent to represent a dominant intellectual norm. The use of this new scholarly methodology to meet new academic needs and illuminate new subject matter has given rise to several discourses such as women's studies, Native American studies, African American studies, gay, lesbian, transgender and global studies.

There has been a growing recognition, both inside and outside academia, that global reality is incorrigibly and irremediably plural and that responsible research and pedagogy must account for and accommodate this fact. The study of the dynamics of racial and ethnic groups who have been denied, at one time or another, full participation, and the full benefits of citizenship, in different societies are worth debating. They are fascinating in themselves, and illuminate the entire spectrum of humanistic inquiry.

The study has attempted to examine the indication of Diaspora Theory and its aspects in literature by discussing Expatriate or Diasporic literature. It has analyzed the Indian contribution to diasporic literature in English to trace out the diasporic as well as recently emerged Bengali sub-group in Indo American Writing.

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